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FUTURE KINDERGARTEN TEACHERS' PEDAGOGICAL SUPPORT IN THE PROCESS OF DISTANCE LEARNING

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The authors reveal the features of a pedagogical support organization for students of higher educational institutions (on the experience of future kindergarten teacher training) in the process of distance learning. The organization of pedagogical support of the distance learning process is carried out in several scopes, namely: analytical and diagnostic (monitoring of distance learning courses; students' characteristics studying; identifying their cognitive and professional interests; determining the individual style of cognitive activity; monitoring educational subjects' interaction); educational (conducting activities that increase distance learning participants' psychological competence); advisory (advising on the development of learning material, advising distance learning participants on development, learning, professional and personal self-determination, on specific issues that arise during learning) and methodological (creating recommendations for teachers to increase student's motivation and pedagogical support organization). The authors show that pedagogical support is not only pedagogical activity, aimed at student's personality self-realization, but also the lecturer's value attitude to each student's personality; respect for their individual identities; perception of the student as an equal one, as a subject of the educational process and their lives, who have a unique inner world and 'Me-concept'; care for future kindergarten teachers' psychological comfort. Providing students with pedagogical support, the lecturer's task is to select the types and means of support that would allow the student to unleash their inner potential without imposing a particular way of solving problems

Keywords: pedagogical support, student, distance learning, educational process, personality, requirements, methods

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1. Introduction

Current events in society (the quarantine in 2020 and the war in 2022) have become a significant challenge for Ukraine and its higher education. All pedagogical staff has faced the need to find optimal ways to organize and implement the educational process in a remote format when student's personality would be the lecturer's focus, and student's cognitive activity would be a priority.

The educational process in higher educational institutions in terms of pedagogical support is fundamentally different from traditional approaches to its organization. Thus, lecturers who implement the concept of support are not into imposing norms, standards, and requirements for the profession. They follow every future kindergarten teacher's professional development, creating conditions for self-realization, supporting their realization, and helping solve their problems.

2. Literature review

Pedagogical support is the subject of research, conducted by numerous scholars who consider it from various aspects. Thus, Yang Yang argues that the category of 'pedagogical support' is interpreted by scholars ambiguously. In particular pedagogical support is con-

sidered as follows: as the teacher's purposeful activities, aimed at providing operational or preventive assistance to the individual in the process of learning and development; as the teacher's activities, realized in the following directions: maintenance of internal conditions (needs, attitudes, abilities) for each person's development and self-development; creation of favorable external conditions for the existence, learning and development of the individual; building a humanistic microsocioal environment in the educational institution through the provision of a favorable psychological climate, active interaction between participants in the educational process; involvement of subjects of interaction in the performance of creative activities, etc [1]. I. Krasnoshchok and T. Kravtsova have revealed the content and structure of future professionals' pedagogical support in the process of their self-realization [2]. Pedagogical support of first-year students at the stage of adaptation to learning has been the subject of research by M. Malkova [3].

A significant amount of scientific works is devoted to the general issues of distance learning content and organization study. Thus, in a collective monograph, V. Kukhareno and V. Bondarenko have set out theoretical and methodological views on the urgent for the entire education system of Ukraine regarding the

issue of implementing the educational process in quarantine, caused by the pandemic of COVID-19. N. Iliina explores the specifics of the organization of feedback during distance learning in the conditions of the higher education institution to ensure the effective interaction of all participants in the educational process. Ji-Yeon Lee explores the current status of learner support in distance education [4]

However, issues related to overcoming learning difficulties remain unresolved. We have analyzed O. Zazymko's and A. Kot's approaches to clarify these issues. The scholars have identified two main groups of difficulties. The first group is one of the personal difficulties, namely those arising due to individual psychological characteristics and learning difficulties that students face directly during the study and acquiring knowledge in distance format [5].

In recent years, interest in the issues of pedagogical support of the individual has been growing. However, the features of the pedagogical support organization for future educators in distance learning are not yet clearly covered in Ukrainian science and practice.

3. The aim and objectives of the study

The aim of the study is to reveal the features of the pedagogical support organization for future kindergarten teachers in the process of distance learning.

To achieve this aim, we should acquire the following objectives:

1. To describe the features of future kindergarten teachers' distance learning organization at Poltava V. G. Korolenko National Pedagogical University.
2. To determine the requirements for pedagogical support of students in the process of distance learning and its objectives.
3. To describe the methods of pedagogical support in the process of future kindergarten teachers' distance learning.

4. Materials and methods

The following methods were used to conduct the study: analysis and generalization of pedagogical sources in order to identify a range of issues that require scientific and methodological support; methods of comparative analysis, interpretation and generalization of facts; comparative and analytical; system analysis for the development of methodology for determining the content, establishing forms and methods of formation of pedagogical support in the process of distance learning.

5. The results of the study

The educational process organization in the conditions of distance learning is based on the independent mastering of the necessary knowledge by the future kindergarten teacher, and the dialogue with the lecturer is carried out with the help of particular means of communication, which can be divided into the following three groups: the first group includes printed materials, audio, and video media; the second group includes computer learning tools (online learning platforms (MOODLE, Google Classroom), electronic textbooks, computer testing, and knowledge control, multimedia); the third one includes video conference (Zoom, Google Meet). Dis-

tance learning is a kind of learning when the lecturer and the student are separated spatially; it is based on the usage of modern information and communication technologies. Among various types of distance learning, distance learning on the platforms of Internet technologies is becoming increasingly popular.

There are different definitions of distance learning in the scientific and pedagogical literature. In our study, we use the following definition: distance learning is a form of learning using computer and telecommunications technologies that provide interaction between lecturers and students at different stages of learning and independent learning on the basis of information network materials [6].

Telecommunication means of the Internet have a number of specific features (openness, accessibility, interactivity, etc.) that must be taken into account when planning and conducting distance learning courses. Students, working with the help of telecommunications in a distance course, often face some problems that require the lecturer's pedagogical assistance and support.

A survey of students at Poltava V. G. Korolenko National Pedagogical University made it possible to identify the following types of difficulties: subjective (personal), namely difficulties, connected with lack of landmark, information for any action, shortcomings of cognitive, emotional, and behavioral components of personality structure; specific difficulties while various activities, when a person can perform the task him/herself, but under the additional stress of volitional, intellectual, moral strength; difficulties, connected with a person's lack of knowledge, experience, abilities to achieve the desired result, which requires the involvement of other actors or abandonment of tasks that can not be solved. The source of the social (environmental) type of difficulties is the environment of the educational institution, in particular, lecturers, administration, friends, and peer groups in higher education institutions, family, and others. Financial difficulties are the following: insufficient number of textbooks, manuals, premises, equipment, technical support, the financial situation of the family, etc.

Support is always individual, so it is difficult to plan and test the effectiveness, as its result may appear much later. However, there are precise requirements for pedagogical support implementation for students in the process of distance learning. Firstly, lecturers must have a clear idea of students' capacity and the availability of working and leisure time and access to Internet resources. Secondly, the question is what issues precisely need to be supported. Thirdly, the dosage of pedagogical support is based on knowledge and understanding of the physical and spiritual nature of the individual, the circumstances of their lives, features of character, language, behavior, as well as their inherent pace of learning. Finally, the introduction of a democratic style of communication, freedom of creative debate, exchange of views, and culture of communication is crucial.

The pedagogical support purpose is to organize a favorable psychological climate for distance learning and help students determine their individual educational trajectories.

Achieving the goal of students' pedagogical support will be possible if the following objectives are fulfilled: the study of students' individual characteristics, features of the relationship of distance learning participants that affect the learning process effectiveness; popularization and transfer to distance learning participants of essential information of different content; creation of favorable conditions for the development of the students' and lecturers' necessary qualities, and the entire adaptation of a particular individual to the conditions of distance learning; providing an individually differentiated approach to learning based on the individual psychological characteristics of an individual.

The organization of pedagogical support of the distance learning process is carried out in several scopes, namely: analytical and diagnostic (monitoring of distance learning courses; students' individual characteristics studying; identifying their cognitive and professional interests; determining the individual style of cognitive activity; monitoring educational subjects' interaction); educational (conducting activities that increase distance learning participants' psychological competence); advisory (advising on the development of learning material, advising distance learning participants on development, learning, professional and personal self-determination, on specific issues that arise during learning) and methodological (creating recommendations for teachers to increase student's motivation and pedagogical support organization).

The fundamental principles of the distance education system are the following: flexibility, modularity, dynamism, adaptability, continuity, creativity, and openness. It is based mainly on obtaining the necessary amount and quality of knowledge and provides a combination of a wide range of traditional and modern information technologies. The usage of these technologies allows students to replenish the list of skills and abilities that will further determine a person's success in any field of activity. These include the ability to plan their activities independently; the ability to make decisions, make choices, and take responsibility for it; the ability to work in the information space (select the necessary information and structure and use it to make decisions on a particular task); and the ability to present the results of activities using information technology; self-education skills [7].

Pedagogical support during distance learning in the process of training future educators at Poltava National Pedagogical University, named after V. G. Korolenko, was carried out as follows. We provided students with pedagogical support during distance learning classes the following way. Along with the main issues that required program knowledge, there were the following creative tasks: Prove or criticize .., Evaluate how good this idea is or how bad it is, Compare and contrast two concepts, etc. We focused attention on the students' ability to ask questions, as it contributed to the problem vision development of the subject content. The main requirements for the question formulation are the following: logic, problem, conciseness, informativeness, etc. The answers to the questions must also be clear, accurate, complete, concise, thorough, informative, and correspond to the essence of the question. The emotional

tone in the classroom was energetic and friendly; the presentation of educational material was emotionally rich, clear, and logical. Simultaneously with the lecturer's psychological position change, the student's status in the educational process changed. The student acted as a 'speaker,' 'scholar,' 'opponent' in the dispute, 'generator of ideas,' 'critic,' 'reviewer.' Thus, the experience of cooperation was formed in the classes. We also drew attention to the fact that the more diverse the forms and methods of teaching were, the more confident future kindergarten teachers became with respect for each other and understanding. At the beginning of distance learning, students' communication was polemical. Yet, after a while, they confidently asked each other questions, expressed their opinions quite professionally, and were critical of their own activities and their classmates' activities evaluation [8].

During practical classes in Poltava V. G. Korolenko National Pedagogical University, lecturers also used various methods of distance learning pedagogical support, which helped overcome students' difficulties:

– Various home assignments and individual assignments allowed the student to choose assignments according to their abilities. It should be noted, that initially students chose tasks of a reproductive nature, but gradually they began to prefer creative assignments.

– The method of 'review'. At the end of each class, students were asked to write a review orally or in writing (optional). This method contributed to the formation of future kindergarten teachers' ability to highlight the main content of educational material and formulate conclusions, as well as perform objectives concisely and competently.

– Work in small groups. It is the work in rooms/halls on the Zoom platform. The lecturer can connect to each of these halls. Participants of one session hall do not hear or see discussions in other halls. The most essential issue here is the division of roles. Thus a 'speaker' is a group leader, who follows the rules during the discussion, reads the tasks, identifies the speaker, and encourages the group to work. A 'secretary' kept records of results and assisted in summarizing and pronouncing. A 'mediator' monitored time and encouraged the group to work. The 'speaker' clearly expressed the group's opinion and reported on the group results. Sometimes, at the request of students, an expert group was selected among the smartest students who worked independently. After that, they reviewed and supplemented the information when the results were announced.

– Brainstorming. It is a well-known technology; its essence is that all participants can express absolutely every idea, even illogical opinions about the issue. Every student could write thoughts on the Zoom board. Students' statements were not criticized at all and were not discussed until the end of the time of making assumptions [8].

The usage of the above-mentioned methods involved students' inclusion in the discussion. Classes were based on the principles of respect for the student and were aimed at students' and lecturers' joint activities. All this contributed to effective teaching; students became more confident in formulating questions and giving their own answers, treated each other with re-

spect and understanding, and were critical in evaluating their activities.

In our opinion, one of the effective methods of providing pedagogical support to students who had difficulties in the process of distance learning was to create a situation of success. Future kindergarten teachers, especially freshmen, have a repeated problem. Thus, they aim to gain a thorough knowledge of professionally oriented fields of study, and the results are not immediately apparent. As a result, there is a problem situation.

Pedagogical support, in this case, was that students were explained that to master the necessary field of study, you need to work long and hard and for more than one year. And in order to monitor their achievements today, students need to find criteria that they can use to determine even slight progress towards the goal, even barely noticeable improvements. If the general goal is not specified and specific intermediate objectives are not defined, it is difficult to capture changes. But if the student focuses not on the ultimate goal but on intermediate objectives, it is a different matter. When the intermediate goal is achieved; the sum of achievements and successes gradually accumulates. Self-esteem and the desire to achieve expand. It encourages future kindergarten teachers to continue working and not stop there. Thus, even the slightest success has a significant impact that motivates and inspires activity.

Students can be offered an approximate algorithm for creating their situation of success. It has been revealed by the author in one of her previous articles. The algorithm is the following:

1. A person can motivate not only others but also him/herself. When there is no desire to work, but you realize the importance of the case, communication with yourself, persuasion or request, and self-help assist in overcoming particular difficulties. The lecturer aims to find the best ways to motivate the student, which would suit his/her personality. Future kindergarten teachers are asked to write several options for self-motivation in a form that depends on the individual, namely sincere requests, unappeasable orders, logical arguments, emotional appeals, or even swearing. The student can choose the best option that suits him/her among the proposed ones.

2. Future kindergarten teachers are invited to break the ultimate goal into several specific intermediate stages and realize the importance of achieving them. It is necessary to set as many specific and realistic goals as possible and strive to achieve them.

3. After that, students are advised to plan to achieve a specific goal or a separate stage. It is suggested to choose a goal of medium difficulty, because the achievement of easy goals will not be perceived as success, and the achievement of too difficult requires a lot of time and effort or is sometimes simply impossible.

4. The next step is to determine the quantitative or qualitative indicators, which can record even minor positive developments.

5. It is necessary to make every effort to successfully complete the task and achieve at least one of the goals. At this stage, the student answers the question: Have you achieved this specific goal? What difficulties did you have to overcome?

6. Finally, the student is invited not to forget to praise him/herself for having achieved even the slightest success (What a good person I am!). Positive emotions related to success are very crucial. Students are invited to 'reward' themselves with something (going to the movies, cafes, etc.) [8–10].

Thus, in the process of using different types and forms of pedagogical support and methods of its implementation, future kindergarten teachers became more active in the classroom, confidently asked questions to both lecturers and classmates, and confidently answered them; it became easier for them to correlate their actions with the lecturers' requirements, to speak to the audience.

It should also be noted, that during the distance educational process, the lecturer, in addition to teaching their subjects, plays the role of a tutor, a facilitator, and a mentor, who must do the following things: coordinate the number of students in groups, acquaint them with procedural requirements; establish contacts with students, identify them, set personal contact with students; prepare teaching materials for students, comment on assignments in Moodle, discuss common mistakes with students; record difficulties and provide the administrator with information about technical errors or problems; assist students, if necessary, in changing the means of information and communication; inform students about the possibility of receiving educational consultations; advise students on studying problems both in person and by phone or e-mail [8].

Elements and resources of Moodle and Zoom allow you to create a learning environment that provides a dialogue between a lecturer and a student and ongoing lecturer's support throughout the course.

6. Conclusions

1. Features of distance learning organization for future kindergarten teachers at Poltava V. G. Korolenko National Pedagogical University are described. It has been found, that they include the usage of various means of communication, namely printed materials, audio and video media, online learning platforms, and video conferencing.

2. Requirements for pedagogical support and its objectives in the process of distance learning are determined. It is established, that the main requirements for pedagogical support are overcoming students' specific difficulties, the dosage of support, democratic style of communication. It has been found, that the study of students' characteristics, the creation of favorable conditions, and providing an individually differentiated approach to teaching are the main objectives of pedagogical support for future educators in the process of distance learning.

3. Methods of pedagogical support of distance learning for future kindergarten teachers are characterized. The usage of creative tasks, varied homework and individual assignments, the method of 'resume,' work in small groups, and 'brainstorming' is described; specific attention has been paid to creating a future educators' situation of success in the learning process.

In summary, it should be noted, that distance education opens opportunities for the future kindergarten teacher and access to modern sources of information,

increases the efficiency of independent learning, provides prospects for acquiring and consolidating various professional skills, needed to work in preschool education, and allows lecturers to implement modern, innovative forms and methods of interactive learning. However, it should be stated, that distance learning will be effective if inno-

vative methods are combined with traditional teaching methods and the lecturer's pedagogical support.

Conflicts of interest

The authors declare that they have no conflicts of interest.

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